

Stegocintractia capitata sp. nov. (*Ustilaginomycetes*) from Germany

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Abstract. After a short revision of the genus *Stegocintractia*, a new species, *S. capitata* on *Juncus capitatus* is described and illustrated. A key to the six known species of *Stegocintractia* is presented.

Key words: *Juncaceae*, new species, smut fungi, *Stegocintractia*, *S. capitata*, taxonomy

Introduction

The genus *Cintractia* s. lat. was revised by Piepenbring *et al.* (1999). Based on molecular and morphological data it was split into four genera: *Cintractia* Cornus s. str., *Gymnocintractia* M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw. (= *Ustanciosporium* Vánky), *Leucocintractia* M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw., and *Stegocintractia* M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw. Two further genera were added: *Pilocintractia* Vánky (2004) and *Portalia* V. González, Vánky & G. Platas (González *et al.*, 2007).

The genus *Stegocintractia* is characterised by sori on plants in *Juncaceae*, in all spikelets or around pedunculi of an infected inflorescence forming black, agglutinated spore masses, powdery on their surface. Young sori are covered by a fungal peridium, sterile stroma is lacking. Infection systemic. Spores single, pigmented (brown), ornamented, without appendages. Host-parasite interaction by intracellular hyphae, coated by an electron-opaque matrix. Mature septa poreless. Five species of *Stegocintractia* are known: 1. *S. hyperborea* (Blytt) M. Piepenbr., on *Luzula* spp. in Europe, Asia, Greenland, 2. *S. junci* (Schwein.) M. Piepenbr., on *Juncus* spp., N & S America, 3. *S. lidii* (Liro) M. Piepenbr., on *Juncus biglumis*,

N. Europe, 4. *S. luzulae* (Sacc.) M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw., on *Luzula* spp., Europe, E. Asia, N. America, and 5. *S. spadicea* (Liro) M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw., on *Luzula alpinopilosa*, Europe.

Smuted *Juncus capitatus* were collected only a few times in Germany: In four cases they were infected by *Tolyposporium junci* (J. Schröt.) Woronin as shown by H. & I. Scholz and H. Jage (comp. Scholz & Scholz 1988: 320). A recent collection of smuted *J. capitatus* turned out to be infected by an unknown species of *Stegocintractia*, which is described below.

Materials and Methods

Sorus and spore characteristics were studied using dried herbarium specimens. Spores were dispersed in a droplet of lactophenol on a microscope slide, covered with a cover glass, gently heated to boiling point to rehydrate the spores, and examined by a light microscope (LM) at 1000× magnification. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), dry spores were placed on double-sided adhesive tape, mounted on a specimen stub, sputter-coated with gold-palladium, c. 20 nm, and examined in a SEM at 10 kV.

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Fig. 1. Sori of *Stegocintractia capitata* in all spikelets of an inflorescence of *Juncus capitatus* (type). Habit and enlarged an infected spikelet. Bars = 1 cm for habit, and 2 mm for detail drawing. Figs 2-3. Spores of *Stegocintractia capitata* on *Juncus capitatus*, in LM and in SEM (from holotype). Bars = 10 µm

Results

Stegocintractia capitata Vánky, Jage, U. Schlüter & Sluschny, sp. nov.

Mycobank # MB 511453.

Sori in spiculis omnibus inflorescentiae matricis conglomeratae massas nigras, globoideas, agglutinatas, 0,5-1 mm diam., sororum superficie pulvereas, glumis plus-minus occultas formantes. *Sporae* singulares, depressae, in visu laterali ellipticae, 5-6,5 µm latae, in visu latitudinali circulares, ovatae usque ad parum irregulares, 7-10,5 × 8,5-11,5 µm, flavido-brunneae; pariete cca. 0,5 µm crasso, leniter moderate dense foveolato excepto parte centrali lateris depressis, ubi verrucoso (sicut in SEM conspicuo). Foveolae in marginibus saepe in seriebus 2-4 parallelis ordinatae.

Typus in matrice *Juncus capitatus* Weigel, Germany, Mecklenburg, Ludwigslust, Motodrom, 14.VII.2007, leg. U. Schlüter & H. Sluschny, comm. B. Schurig to H. Jage. Holotypus H.U.V. 21 504, isotypus TUB 019 014.

Sori (Fig. 1) in all spikelets of a congested inflorescence, forming black, globoid, agglutinated spore masses with powdery surface, 0,5-1 mm in diam., more or less hidden by the glumes. *Spores* (Figs 2-3) single, flattened, in side view elliptic, 5-6,5 µm wide, in plane view circular, ovate to slightly irregular, 7-10,5 × 8,5-11,5 µm, yellowish brown; wall c. 0,5 µm thick, finely, moderately densely foveolate excepting the central part of the flattened sides where it is verrucose as seen in SEM. Foveolae on the rims are often arranged in 2-4 parallel rows.

On Juncaceae: *Juncus capitatus*; Europe (Germany). Known only from the type locality.

Key to the species of *Stegocintractia*

1	On <i>Juncus</i>	2
1*	On <i>Luzula</i>	4
2	Sori around floral pedicels, only rarely in the spikelets	<i>S. junci</i>
2*	Sori in the spikelets	3
3	Spores 15-21 μm long	<i>S. lidii</i>
3*	Spores 8.5-11.5 μm long	<i>S. capitata</i>
4	Spores verruculose-echinulate	<i>S. hyperborea</i>
4*	Spores foveolate	5
5	Spores 20-30 (-32) μm long	<i>S. luzulae</i>
5*	Spores 13-21 μm long	<i>S. spadicea</i>

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